

Restoring Traditional Arable Practices like 'Bolle Akkers': The Role of Agroforestry in Revitalizing Heritage Farming Systems

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Bolle akker (field) in the Waasland

Bolle akkers (fields) are a unique landscape feature of the Waasland, a historical region in northern Belgium. These square, slightly elevated fields were likely created in the 14th and 15th centuries to improve the drainage and fertility of the poorly water-permeable loamy soil. This ingenious design combines functionality and durability, reflecting the agricultural innovations of the time. To construct the raised surface, soil was partially excavated along the four sides of a plot and plowed inward. On at least two sides, wide and deep ditches were dug, starting at a depth of 60-80 cm and extending 3-4 meters in width. From this level, a central dividing ditch was dug, measuring 1-1.5 meters in both width and depth, creating two terraces approximately 1 meter wide on either side. These terraces were planted with hedgerows of species such as beech, willow, oak, alder, plane, and poplar. These hedgerows provided wind protection, timber, and enhanced the distinctive character of the landscape. For centuries, bolle fields—often surrounded by pollarded willows or poplars—shaped the scenery of the Waasland. Today, however, they are under threat from land consolidation and intensive farming practices. Agroforestry offers an opportunity to preserve bolle fields. By combining crops such as clover, wheat, cover crops, and hemp with rows of trees, a sustainable system is created that stores biomass and carbon, enhances biodiversity, and positions agriculture as a buffer between natural areas, industry, and residential zones. An economic model built around agroforestry could make bolle fields viable again. In doing so, these fields would not only retain their ecological value but also remain a vital part of the Waasland's rich agricultural heritage.

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